
Diffusion Model for Electromagnetic Field Reconstruction

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Abstract

With the continuous evolution of wireless communication generations, electromagnetic field (EMF) exposure has emerged as a critical concern, especially in urban environments. Accurate reconstruction of EMF exposure maps remains a significant challenge due to the limited availability of measurement sensors and the complex propagation characteristics of EM waves. In this study, I propose a approach that utilizes a diffusion model for EMF reconstruction, tailored to capture the spatial variations of EMF in diverse topologies. Unlike traditional methods, the proposed diffusion-based framework not only enhances the accuracy of exposure maps but also provides a robust understanding of propagation dynamics. The reconstructed maps are compared with baseline kriging method to evaluate the model's performance under various scenarios. The results demonstrate that the diffusion model offers superior accuracy and reliability, making it a promising tool to address concerns about EMF exposure in next-generation wireless networks.

1. Introduction

Wireless communication systems have become an integral part of modern life, facilitating connectivity across diverse applications. Monitoring radio-frequency electromagnetic field (RF-EMF) exposure has thus become a crucial aspect of understanding and managing the impact of these systems on public health and the environment. In urban areas, a multitude of EMF sources, including WiFi and successive generations of mobile communication technologies, contribute to the overall exposure landscape (Gajšek et al., 2015). The evolution of wireless networks toward higher frequencies and denser infrastructure has introduced new challenges, necessitating robust monitoring and compliance

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with human exposure standards set by organizations such as the International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) and the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE). These regulatory frameworks aim to ensure that both mobile devices and base stations operate within safe exposure limits, underscoring the importance of accurate EMF assessment and mitigation strategies in the context of emerging wireless generations.

While sensor networks and on-site measurements play a vital role, their scope is inherently limited, providing only partial insights into EMF exposure. For instance, Figure 1 illustrates a measurement device deployed in downtown Toronto, demonstrating a practical example of how EMF data collection can be done in a dense urban environment. In urban landscapes, factors such as the arrangement of buildings, road networks, moving vehicles, and overall city design greatly influence the placement of base stations and mobile devices. Therefore, developing a reliable power map to analyze RF-EMF exposure necessitates incorporating these complexities. A significant challenge is constructing exposure maps from a sparse array of sensor measurements that vary dynamically with environmental topology and network traffic.

Figure 1. On-site EMF measurement in Downtown Toronto

In this study, we aim to evaluate RF-EMF exposure within

a 1 km × 1 km area using 100 fixed receivers uniformly distributed across the York University campus in Toronto, Canada. The analysis is performed using a diffusion-based model (Ho et al., 2020; Lugmayr et al., 2022) that incorporates the sparse EMF measurements as a critical input parameter, enabling the reconstruction of a complete exposure heatmap. This methodology is inspired to capture the intricate features of electromagnetic wave propagation, including diffraction, shadowing, and reflections influenced by buildings, materials, roadways, and other campus-specific environmental factors.

In addition to the diffusion-based model, traditional reconstruction techniques such as kriging (Stein, 1999b) are implemented for comparative analysis. The base stations are assumed to operate at a frequency of 2.115 GHz with a bandwidth of 10 MHz, allowing for the generation of precise exposure maps. Moreover, this study’s methodology is adaptable to a variety of city layouts, ranging from mid-dense to densely populated urban areas, as well as rural environments. This versatility underscores the broader applicability of the approach to diverse geographical settings and wireless communication infrastructures. The main contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- Generating a new simulated dataset using data from the Spectrum Management System provided by (ISED) Canada (Innovation & Canada, 2024). This dataset includes detailed information about all base stations across Canada. From this data, we extracted information for six base stations within our area of interest and utilized it to generate 6,000 heatmaps.
- Developing a diffusion-based model utilizing a U-Net structure with deep convolutional layers and time embeddings to estimate EMF exposure maps based on sparse measurements from receiver points and base station data.

2. Related Works

Accurately estimating RF power maps in geographic regions is a computationally intensive task, particularly in urban environments. Traditional methods, such as ray-tracing techniques and empirical or semi-empirical models like close-in (CI) and floating intercept (FI), are commonly used to predict power coverage by modeling the propagation and distribution of radio signals (MacCartney et al., 2013; Pier-santi et al., 2012). Deterministic models like ray-tracing approaches are recognized for their precision but are computationally demanding, relying heavily on detailed three-dimensional (3D) environmental models (Balanis, 2012). Ray-tracing methods, based on high-frequency approximations of Maxwell’s equations, simulate wave interactions such as reflection, diffraction, and scattering. However, their

significant computational requirements often limit their feasibility in large-scale or dynamic scenarios, leading to the adoption of simplified stochastic or hybrid approaches in network simulators for coverage mapping (Yun & Iskander, 2015). Data-driven interpolation techniques rely on available measurements at specific points to predict values at non-measured locations using signal processing methods. For instance, kriging is a widely used approach that incorporates physical modeling to perform spatial interpolation (Stein, 1999a). Other research has explored convolutional neural network (CNN)-based Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) to estimate power spectrum maps for urban cognitive radio networks, leveraging under-sampled data as input for reconstruction (Goodfellow et al., 2014).

This paper introduces a novel approach for reconstructing EMF maps using diffusion models (Lugmayr et al., 2022), which require significantly fewer measurement points compared to traditional methods. Unlike existing techniques such as kriging or GANs, the diffusion model leverages sparse data to generate accurate and comprehensive RF exposure maps. By incorporating spatial features directly into the modeling process, the proposed method overcomes the limitations of simplified propagation models, like the inverse polynomial law. The propagation of radio signals and the calculation of these maps are based on the Friis transmission formula, which ensures an accurate estimation of power levels. Furthermore, the diffusion model reduces dependency on pre-simulated full maps, offering a scalable and computationally efficient solution for dynamic urban environments. This approach represents a significant advancement in the field by enabling precise EMF map reconstruction with minimal measurement inputs, making it highly applicable to real-world scenarios.

3. Dataset

To prepare the dataset for this study, data from (Innovation & Canada, 2024) which includes information on base stations (BSs) across Canada, was used. The area of interest was 1km * 1km and was narrowed to the York University campus as depicted in Figure 2. The transmitters are assumed to use an isotropic antenna, producing omnidirectional radio waves. Each base station can operate across various frequencies and bandwidths to support different wireless technologies. For this study, we standardized the frequency to 2.115 GHz and the bandwidth to 10 MHz for all six base stations in the study area.

Figure 2. Base stations located in York University(Keele Campus)

To calculate the electromagnetic field propagation, 100 receiver points were uniformly distributed across the study area as shown in Figure 3. I considered a static environment such that no mobility between the transmitter and receivers is taken into account at a certain time step. Each receiver point was considered to be placed at a height of 1.8 meters to account for line-of-sight (LoS) calculations. Also, the height of each base station was determined as the sum of the structure height and the antenna height. The total distance L between a base station and a receiver point was calculated using the following formula:

$$L = \sqrt{(h_{BS} - h_{RP})^2 + d_{horizontal}^2} \quad (1)$$

where:

- h_{BS} is the height of the base station, obtained by adding the structure height and the antenna height, h_{RP} is the height of the receiver point, set at 1.8 meters.
- $d_{horizontal}$ is the horizontal distance between the base station and the receiver point, calculated using the geodesic formula.

Figure 3. 100 Uniformly placed receiver points

To generate the power density maps for the area of interest, we calculated the received power density ($W_{r,dv}$) based on the total distances between base stations (BSs) and receiver points (RPs) calculated in eq.1 as well as the transmission characteristics. The path loss was modeled as $L^{-\alpha}$, where α is the path loss exponent. The received power (P_r) at an RP was calculated using the Friis transmission equation (Shaw, 2013):

$$P_r = P_t + G_t + 10 \log_{10} (\zeta \cdot L^{-\alpha} \cdot X_{fading}), \quad (2)$$

where P_t is the transmission power (in dBm), G_t is the transmitter antenna gain (in dBi), $\zeta = (\frac{\lambda}{4\pi})^2$ is the free-space path loss factor with wavelength λ , and X_{fading} represents small-scale fading modeled as a Rayleigh distribution. The received power was then converted from dBm to Watts and divided by the effective aperture ($A_e = \frac{\lambda^2}{4\pi}$) of the antenna to calculate the power density:

$$W_{r,dv} = \frac{10^{\frac{P_r}{10}} \cdot 10^{-3}}{A_e}. \quad (3)$$

The total received power density for each RP was computed by summing contributions from all BSs, and the results were interpolated to create a continuous power density heatmap over the region. By varying the path loss exponent α from 2 to 4 and modifying the random seed for Rayleigh fading, we generated a diverse dataset required for training the model. This approach allowed us to simulate a wide range of real-world propagation scenarios and ensure robust model performance. Figure 4 gives an example of exposure maps when the transmitters in this specific area are considered and path loss equals 2.2. Each map has a dimension of 512 height, 512 width, and 3 RGB color channels.

Figure 4. RF-EMF exposure map

To generate the undersampled sensor map images, we con-

sidered subsets of the receiver points corresponding to 10%, 20%, and 30% of the total measurement points. To capture RF-EMF reconstruction using sparse measurements we introduced a binary mask as an additional input to the diffusion model. The binary mask is used to filter the EMF exposure map, as the primary goal is RF-EMF exposure map reconstruction. An example of the image with applied mask where only 10% of measurements are considered is shown in Figure 5. It is noteworthy that even in the most optimistic case, when 30% of the total measurement points are used, the sensor coverage accounts for only a small fraction of the area in the reference image.

Figure 5. Sparse RF-EMF exposure map with 10% of measurements

4. Preliminaries: Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models

In this work, I utilize diffusion models, specifically Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models (DDPM) (Lugmayr et al., 2022), as a generative approach for reconstructing heatmaps from sparse or noisy inputs. These models learn the underlying data distribution from a training dataset and leverage a forward and reverse diffusion process to transform random noise into high-quality outputs. The generative capability of DDPM lies in its ability to model the forward process of adding noise and the reverse process of iterative denoising.

4.1. Forward Diffusion Process

The forward diffusion process gradually corrupts a clean image \mathbf{x}_0 into pure Gaussian noise $\mathbf{x}_T \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$ over T discrete time steps. At each step t , Gaussian noise is added, and the resulting sample \mathbf{x}_t is defined as:

$$q(\mathbf{x}_t | \mathbf{x}_{t-1}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_t; \sqrt{1 - \beta_t} \mathbf{x}_{t-1}, \beta_t \mathbf{I}), \quad (4)$$

where β_t is a variance schedule controlling the noise in-

tensity at each step. The transformation smooths the input data distribution over time, effectively convolving it with Gaussian noise. Importantly, intermediate steps \mathbf{x}_t can be computed directly from the initial sample \mathbf{x}_0 using:

$$q(\mathbf{x}_t | \mathbf{x}_0) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_t; \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{x}_0, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) \mathbf{I}), \quad (5)$$

where

$$\bar{\alpha}_t = \prod_{s=1}^t (1 - \beta_s).$$

This formulation simplifies data generation during training and enables efficient sampling of noisy and clean data pairs.

4.2. Reverse Denoising Process

The reverse diffusion process starts from Gaussian noise \mathbf{x}_T and iteratively reconstructs the original image \mathbf{x}_0 . The reverse process is parameterized as:

$$p_\theta(\mathbf{x}_{t-1} | \mathbf{x}_t) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}; \boldsymbol{\mu}_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t), \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t)), \quad (6)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t)$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t)$ are modeled using a neural network that predicts the mean and variance of the distribution. This neural network operates on noisy images of the same size and gradually refines them at each step.

4.3. Training Objective

The DDPM is trained by minimizing the Evidence Lower Bound (ELBO) on the log-likelihood of the data:

$$\mathbb{E}[-\log p_\theta(\mathbf{x}_0)] \leq \mathbb{E}_q \left[-\log \frac{p_\theta(\mathbf{x}_0:T)}{q(\mathbf{x}_{1:T} | \mathbf{x}_0)} \right] \quad (7)$$

This objective decomposes into the following terms:

$$\begin{aligned} L = & \underbrace{D_{\text{KL}}(q(\mathbf{x}_T | \mathbf{x}_0) \| p(\mathbf{x}_T))}_{L_T} \\ & + \sum_{t>1} \underbrace{D_{\text{KL}}(q(\mathbf{x}_{t-1} | \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_0) \| p_\theta(\mathbf{x}_{t-1} | \mathbf{x}_t))}_{L_{t-1}} \\ & - \underbrace{\log p_\theta(\mathbf{x}_0 | \mathbf{x}_1)}_{L_0} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The term L_{t-1} trains the model to reverse a single diffusion step, leveraging the fact that $q(\mathbf{x}_{t-1} | \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_0)$ is also Gaussian, enabling closed-form expressions for the objective.

Ho et al (Ho et al., 2020) introduced a simplified parameterization of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t)$ to predict the cumulative noise ϵ added to \mathbf{x}_t :

Algorithm 1 Training for DDPM

Input: Data distribution $q(x_0)$, number of timesteps T

Output: Trained model ϵ_θ

repeat

 Sample $x_0 \sim q(x_0)$

 Sample $t \sim \text{Uniform}(\{1, \dots, T\})$

 Sample $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$

 Compute $\nabla_\theta \|\epsilon - \epsilon_\theta(\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}x_0 + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}\epsilon, t)\|^2$

 Update θ using gradient descent

until converged

Algorithm 2 Sampling for DDPM

Input: Trained model ϵ_θ , number of timesteps T

Output: Generated sample x_0

Sample $x_T \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$

for $t = T, \dots, 1$ **do**

if $t > 1$ **then**

 Sample $z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$

end if

 Compute $x_{t-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(x_t - \frac{1 - \alpha_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon_\theta(x_t, t) \right) + \sigma_t z$

end for

return x_0

$$\mu_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{x}_t - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t) \right) \quad (9)$$

They also demonstrated that the model can be trained by predicting the noise ϵ added to create \mathbf{x}_t . The simplified training objective becomes:

$$L_{\text{simple}} = \mathbb{E}_{t, \mathbf{x}_0, \epsilon} [\|\epsilon - \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t)\|_2^2] \quad (10)$$

This approach significantly reduces computational complexity and maintains high performance.

To summarize, as shown in **Algorithm 1**, the training process involves sampling a clean image x_0 from the data distribution $q(x_0)$ and adding noise through a predefined variance schedule to generate a noisy sample x_t . The model is trained to predict the added noise ϵ using the gradient descent optimization of a simplified objective, $\|\epsilon - \epsilon_\theta(x_t, t)\|^2$, iteratively updating the model parameters θ . In **Algorithm 2**, the sampling process begins with Gaussian noise $x_T \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$ and iteratively applies the reverse diffusion steps. At each timestep t , the model predicts the mean of the less noisy sample x_{t-1} , progressively refining the sample until a high-quality output x_0 is reconstructed.

4.4. Time Representation

Time embeddings are essential in diffusion models for encoding temporal information, enabling the model to distinguish between different timesteps in the reverse diffusion

process. During denoising, the model must know the specific timestep t to correctly interpret the noise level and reconstruct the data. To achieve this, sinusoidal positional embeddings are employed, mapping discrete timesteps into high-dimensional continuous representations. The embeddings are computed as:

$$\text{embedding}(t) = \left[\sin\left(\frac{t}{10000^{\frac{i}{d}}}\right), \cos\left(\frac{t}{10000^{\frac{i}{d}}}\right) \right], \quad (11)$$

where i is the embedding dimension index and d is the total embedding dimension. This formulation provides a smooth, periodic representation of time, ensuring that the embeddings vary continuously with timestep and are interpretable by the model. These embeddings allow the model to accurately infer the relationship between timestep-specific noise and the underlying data distribution, thereby improving the denoising accuracy and overall reconstruction quality.

4.5. Image Reconstruction from Sparse Measurements

The goal of reconstruction is to predict missing regions in a heat map using sparse measurements as a condition. I utilize a trained unconditional DDPM. The ground truth map is denoted as \mathbf{x}_0 , where known sparse measurements are represented as $\mathbf{m} \odot \mathbf{x}_0$ and missing regions are $(1 - \mathbf{m}) \odot \mathbf{x}_0$, with \mathbf{m} being a binary mask.

Each reverse step of the DDPM depends only on \mathbf{x}_t , allowing the known regions $\mathbf{m} \odot \mathbf{x}_t$ to be updated independently while preserving the properties of the underlying distribution. By leveraging the Markovian nature of the forward process, we sample intermediate states \mathbf{x}_t using:

$$\mathbf{x}_t \sim \mathcal{N}(\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{x}_0, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) \mathbf{I}), \quad (12)$$

where $\bar{\alpha}_t$ controls the variance schedule. Using this, we define the reconstruction step as follows:

$$\mathbf{x}_{\text{known}, t-1} \sim \mathcal{N}(\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{x}_0, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) \mathbf{I}), \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{\text{unknown}, t-1} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t), \Sigma_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t)), \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{t-1} = \mathbf{m} \odot \mathbf{x}_{\text{known}, t-1} + (1 - \mathbf{m}) \odot \mathbf{x}_{\text{unknown}, t-1}. \quad (15)$$

Here, $\mathbf{x}_{\text{known}, t-1}$ is sampled directly using the sparse measurements, while $\mathbf{x}_{\text{unknown}, t-1}$ is inferred from the DDPM. This ensures that known regions remain fixed while missing regions are reconstructed iteratively.

5. Network Architecture

The network architecture illustrated in Figure 6 is based on a U-Net structure, which has been modified to suit the

Algorithm 3 Image Reconstruction Using Sparse Measurements

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1:  $x_T \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{I})$ 
2: for  $t = T, \dots, 1$  do
3:   for  $u = 1, \dots, U$  do
4:      $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{I})$  if  $t > 1$ , else  $\epsilon = 0$ 
5:      $x_{\text{known}, t-1} = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} x_0 + (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) \epsilon$ 
6:      $\mathbf{z} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{I})$  if  $t > 1$ , else  $\mathbf{z} = 0$ 
7:      $x_{\text{unknown}, t-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left( x_t - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon_\theta(x_t, t) \right) + \sigma_t \mathbf{z}$ 
8:      $x_{t-1} = \mathbf{m} \odot x_{\text{known}, t-1} + (1 - \mathbf{m}) \odot x_{\text{unknown}, t-1}$ 
9:     if  $u < U$  and  $t > 1$  then
10:       $x_t \sim \mathcal{N}(\sqrt{1 - \beta_{t-1}} x_{t-1}, \beta_{t-1} \mathbf{I})$ 
11:     end if
12:   end for
13: end for
14: return  $x_0$ 

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requirements of heatmap reconstruction from sparse measurements. The encoder and decoder are connected through skip connections, which include feature concatenation to preserve spatial details and enhance reconstruction quality.

Figure 6. Network Architecture of Proposed Diffusion Model

The **encoder path** consists of a series of convolutional layers designed to extract hierarchical spatial features from the input heatmap data. Each stage of the encoder contains two convolutional layers, each with a kernel size of 3, a stride of 1, and padding of 1, ensuring the spatial dimensions remain consistent throughout. These layers are followed by batch normalization to stabilize training and a LeakyReLU activation to maintain non-linear properties. Max pooling with a kernel size of 2 and stride of 2 is applied after each stage to downsample the spatial dimensions, allowing the network to capture larger contextual information. The encoder is designed with progressively increasing feature channels across its stages, enabling the extraction of complex spatial patterns.

The **bottleneck**, positioned between the encoder and decoder, comprises two convolutional layers with a kernel size of 3, stride of 1, and padding of 1, followed by batch normalization and LeakyReLU activation. This module processes the downsampled feature maps from the encoder and incorporates time embeddings to integrate temporal information into the feature representations. The time embeddings,

generated using sinusoidal positional encodings, are passed through two fully connected layers and subsequently added to the bottleneck feature maps, ensuring that the reconstruction process is conditioned on the diffusion timestep.

The **decoder** begins by upsampling the bottleneck features using transposed convolutional layers, which increase the spatial dimensions progressively until they match the original input size. Each upsampling step is followed by convolutional layers with batch normalization and LeakyReLU activation. Skip connections from the encoder stages, which retain spatial features, are concatenated with the upsampled feature maps in the decoder. This operation ensures that the network effectively reintroduces spatial details that were lost during the encoder’s downsampling process while maintaining high-level semantic information. To conclude, Table 1 summarizes the key parameters and configurations used in the design and training of the proposed diffusion model for heatmap reconstruction.

Table 1. Network Parameters.

Parameters	Value
Optimizer	AdamW
Learning Rate	0.0004
Kernel Size	3x3
Non-Linearity	LeakyReLU
Upsampling	Nearest Neighbor
Downsampling	Max Pooling with Stride 2
Loss Function	Mean Squared Error (MSE)
Time Embedding	Sinusoidal Positional Encoding
Skip Connections	Concatenation
Epochs	20
Batch Size	64
Feature Channels	64, 128, 256, 512 (progressive)
Number of Time Steps	1000
Noise Schedule	Linear (Beta: 0.0001 to 0.01)
Total Number of Images	6000
Input Samples	2500
Test Set	500

6. Simulation Results

To assess the performance of proposed framework for reconstructing heatmaps from sparse measurements, I employ the **Mean Squared Error (MSE)** as the primary metric. MSE quantifies the average squared difference between the observed and predicted values and is defined as:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(Y_i - \hat{Y}_i \right)^2, \quad (16)$$

where Y_i denotes the ground truth value, \hat{Y}_i represents the predicted value, and n is the total number of points in the heatmap. MSE penalizes large errors quadratically, making it sensitive to significant deviations between predicted and true values. The model’s ability to handle varying levels of sparsity is evaluated by generating heatmaps with different masking probabilities as depicted in Figure 7. These masking probabilities represent the percentage of data points removed from the original heatmap, creating sparsely sampled inputs. The masked regions are represented as white spaces, while the colored regions indicate the remaining data used for reconstruction.

Also, Figure 8 illustrates the reconstructed PDM, the error map comparing ground truth and reconstructed values, and the ground truth map itself. The middle panel shows the reconstructed PDM using only 10% of the measurement points, demonstrating the model’s ability to infer missing spatial information from sparse data. The left panel depicts the error map, highlighting the absolute differences between the reconstructed map and the ground truth. It reveals that the majority of the reconstruction error is concentrated around high-gradient areas, indicating the challenge of capturing rapid spatial variations. Finally, the right panel presents the received power density map (ground truth) as a reference for evaluating the reconstruction accuracy.

Figure 9 presents the reconstructed power density map generated using the Kriging interpolation method (Stein, 1999a). While Kriging is a robust interpolation approach that effectively estimates spatial distributions from sparse measurement data, it tends to oversmooth the reconstructed map, which leads to a loss of fine-grained details and localized variations in the power density.

In contrast, our proposed diffusion model (as shown in Figure 8) excels in preserving spatial details and accurately reconstructing localized variations. The diffusion model leverages a data-driven approach combined with skip connections to retain high-frequency spatial features while progressively refining the reconstruction. This enables it to outperform the Kriging method, particularly in regions with complex variations, providing a more detailed and accurate representation of the spatial distribution.

Table 2. MSE Comparison in Two Approaches

Sensors (%)	Kriging	Proposed Model
20%	3.754×10^{-1}	2.451×10^{-5}
40%	3.271×10^{-1}	1.945×10^{-5}
60%	2.957×10^{-1}	1.572×10^{-5}

7. Conclusion

The study introduces a diffusion-based generative model for reconstructing sparse power density heatmaps with enhanced accuracy and detail preservation. Unlike traditional interpolation methods such as kriging, which rely on simplistic spatial assumptions, the proposed model employs a generator architecture with skip connections and time conditioning, enabling accurate heatmap reconstruction even with sparse input data covering as little as 20% of the reference map area. This approach not only captures intricate spatial relationships but also effectively preserves fine-grained details. By leveraging diffusion dynamics, the model mitigates the limitations of sparse sampling without requiring extensive training datasets or prior assumptions about spatial distributions. Future advancements will focus on further optimizing computational efficiency and exploring the integration of adaptive loss functions and multi-scale modeling to enhance the reconstruction quality across varying levels of sparsity and complexity.

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Figure 7. Sparse Heatmaps with Different Levels of Masking. The left, middle, and right images represent masking probabilities of 0.8, 0.6, and 0.4, respectively, demonstrating the impact of varying sparsity levels on the input heatmap.

Figure 8. Comparison of Reconstructed Maps. Middle: Reconstructed PDM (10% of measurement points). Right: Error Map (Ground Truth vs. Reconstructed). Left: Received Power Density Map (Ground Truth).

Figure 9. Reconstructed Power Density Map using the Kriging Method

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